

Coding Summary by File Beyond Open Research II 23/09/2025 12:06

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Dataset

Files\workshop 2 session 2 Values exercise RAW DATA

Code

Codes\Autocoded Themes\individuals

	Yes	0.0526	2			
				1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Advertising individuals roles internally (newsletter)						
				2	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction						

Codes\Autocoded Themes\individuals\advertising individuals roles

	No	0.0263	1			
				1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Advertising individuals roles internally (newsletter)						

Codes\Autocoded Themes\individuals\assessing individuals satisfaction

	No	0.0263	1			
				1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction						

Codes\Autocoded Themes\management

	Yes	0.0526	2			
				1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
[solve] power disbalance management within teams						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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2 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

training for people management

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\management\\people management

No 0.0263 1

1 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

training for people management

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\management\\power disbalance management

No 0.0263 1

1 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

[solve] power disbalance management within teams

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\satisfaction

Yes 0.0526 2

1 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

Job satisfaction

2 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\satisfaction\\assessing individuals satisfaction

No 0.0263 1

1 NV 19/08/2025 09:11

Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\satisfaction\job satisfaction

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0263	1		1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Job satisfaction						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\teams

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.0526	2		1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
More funding/grants awarded to multiple teams						
				2	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\teams\evaluating team development

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0263	1		1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\teams\multiple teams

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0263	1		1	NV	19/08/2025 09:11
More funding/grants awarded to multiple teams						

Codes\\Values Collaboration

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.1578	6		1	JS	19/08/2025 09:35
Meaningful collaboration						
				2	JS	19/08/2025 09:35
Supportiue networks						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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				3	JS	19/08/2025 09:42
More skills/knowledge sharing between groups + collaborators						

				4	JS	19/08/2025 09:42
Greater visibility of what teams do (supported by cross organisation meetings/communications + systems)						

				5	JS	19/08/2025 09:42
Mora publications co-authored by different/multidisciplinary groups						

				6	JS	19/08/2025 09:42
More funding/grants awarded to multiple teams						

Codes\\Values Diversity

No	0.0263	1
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				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:41
Diversity of team not by roles but by background						

Codes\\Values Equity

No	0.0263	1
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				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:42
[solve] power disbalance management within teams						

Codes\\Values Recognition

No	0.1315	5
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				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:34
Opportunities						

				2	JS	19/08/2025 09:35
Appropriate systems of credit						

				3	JS	19/08/2025 09:40
Rewards						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Visibility and transparency				4	JS	19/08/2025 09:41
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Pre-registration with various tools				5	JS	19/08/2025 09:50
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Codes\\Values Wellbeing & motivation

No	0.1578	6
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Managed risk taking				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:44
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Job satisfaction				2	JS	19/08/2025 09:41
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Advertising individuals roles internally (newsletter)				3	JS	19/08/2025 09:43
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Mental health / people first				4	JS	19/08/2025 09:43
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training for people management				5	JS	19/08/2025 09:43
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Evaluating team development assessing individuals satisfaction				6	JS	19/08/2025 09:43
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Codes\\workshop 2 session 2 Values exercise RAW DATA\\Values

No	0.5000	19
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				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:11
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Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\workshop 2 session 2 Values exercise RAW DATA\\Votes

	No	0.5000	19			
				1	JS	19/08/2025 09:11
